

Data Governance Checklist for Institutions

The following is a list of questions relating to 14 areas of data governance for institutions. Ask yourself these questions to make sure good data governance is in place for your institution.

Existing Data Governance

- Do you have a data governance framework or policy?
- Do you have any existing data-related policies, such as a data management policy?
- Do you have a data governance committee or group set up?
- Do you have a good understanding of data governance?

Roles and Responsibilities

- Have you identified a data custodian for the data produced?
- Do you have money or investment for data governance?
- Do you know the value of your data?

Training

- Is training provided for those who are managing data?

Data Ownership

- Have you identified who owns the data, which could be (but not limited to) the institution, the researcher or a third party?

Data Location

- Have you identified where the data is being stored?
- Does the data need to be stored in Australia?
- Are you aware of the requirements that different states impose on the management and/or handling of data?

Data Handling and Curation

- Do you have a data handling policy?
- Have you identified the reasons why the data should be managed?
- Are you aware of the benefits that managing data will bring?
- Do you have any incentives for data management?

Data Sensitivity, Classification and Ethics

- Is your ethics committee aware of and/or involved in determining data governance requirements?

Data Storage and Retention

- Does the data need to be retained for a period of time before it can be destroyed?
- Do you have any data retention protocols?
- Do you know where your data is?

Data Access

- Do you have a template for [data sharing agreements](#) (DSAs) for requests for datasets?
- Do you know who has access to your data?

Licencing, Copyright and IP

- Can you identify who owns the copyright of the data?
- Do you know who is protecting your data?
- Do you know how well-protected your data is?

Data Reuse

- Have you identified how the data is likely to be reused?

Tools to Support Data Governance

- Does the institution have tools such as IT software to support the management of data?

Data Type, Format and Size

- Do you understand the nature and type of data that is being collected and used by the project, given that they will impact the sensitivity, ethics, licensing and handling of the data and access to it?
- What disciplines does the data you are collecting belong to (e.g. STEM, HASS, Indigenous Studies, or Non-Traditional Research Outputs or NTROs)?
- Have the [FAIR principles](#) been considered for the management and governance of the data?
- Have you considered the [CARE principles](#) in relation to the governance of your data?
- Have you considered the [TRUST principles](#) and their impact on the governance of your data?

Risks

- Have you identified any risks involved with the creation and sharing of your data?
- Has a risk assessment been performed? Have the risks been documented?